

Legal Risks of Intellectual Property and Digital Plagiarism in Mozambique: Case Study of the Higher Institute of Training, Research and Science (2022 – 2024)

Jorge Manuel Tembe¹, Edvino Carlos Bunge²

^{1,2}Higher Institute of Training, Research and Science (ISFIC), and Ministry of the Interior

ABSTRACT : This study aims to analyze the legal risks associated with intellectual property infringement and digital plagiarism in the context of Mozambican higher education, focusing on the Higher Institute of Training, Research, and Science (ISFIC), from 2022 to 2024. The research addresses the main national legal instruments, highlighting Law No. 9/2022, which regulates copyright and related rights in Mozambique, as well as the Mozambican Penal Code, which classifies plagiarism as a criminal offense. In addition to the theoretical and normative survey, a qualitative case study was conducted at ISFIC, involving faculty, researchers, and students, to assess the level of knowledge about the legal risks of misusing intellectual property. Data were collected through semi-structured interviews and questionnaires and analyzed using content analysis. The results indicate institutional weaknesses in combating plagiarism and a limited understanding, among the academic community, of the legal implications of intellectual property infringement. The study concludes that more robust institutional policies and ongoing awareness-raising actions are needed to promote a culture of academic integrity, legal compliance, and the appreciation of scientific production.

KEYWORDS: Digital plagiarism. Intellectual property. Higher education. Copyright.

INTRODUCTION

Intellectual property (IP) has become one of the fundamental pillars of scientific, educational, and technological development in contemporary societies, especially in the digital context. With the increasing production and dissemination of content in electronic media, new legal, ethical, and institutional challenges arise related to copyright protection and the prevention of digital plagiarism (Santos & Macie, 2023). In higher education in Mozambique, institutions face significant legal risks when they fail to implement effective mechanisms to prevent and manage these issues.

Mozambican law recognizes and protects copyright through Law No. 9/2022, of July 29, which updates the legal framework for protecting intellectual property, adapting it to international standards and current technological requirements. This law covers the author's moral and patrimonial rights, as well as related rights, reinforcing the need for registration, responsible use, and combating unauthorized reproduction of intellectual works.

Digital plagiarism, defined as the misuse of digital content without proper attribution, has become a common practice in academia, driven by easy access to online information and the lack of effective institutional academic integrity policies (Mabunda & Chivambo, 2022). This practice not only undermines the scientific credibility of institutions but can also generate legal, administrative, and reputational consequences.

This article aims to analyze the legal risks associated with the violation of intellectual property rights and the practice of digital plagiarism at the Instituto Superior de Formação, Investigação e Ciência (ISFIC), during the period from 2022 to 2024. It seeks to

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identify the existing institutional mechanisms, the challenges faced and propose measures for more effective management of academic integrity, in accordance with current legislation and international best practices.

The digital age has profoundly transformed the ways in which intellectual content is created, disseminated, and appropriated. With the advent of information and communication technologies, it has become easier to produce, share, and replicate academic, scientific, and technical content, significantly increasing the challenges of protecting intellectual property and controlling plagiarism, especially in academia.

In Mozambique, these challenges are particularly acute in the context of higher education, where many institutions are still in the process of consolidating scientific integrity and copyright protection policies. The democratization of access to the internet and digital databases has, on the one hand, stimulated academic production, but, on the other, also facilitated the occurrence of inappropriate practices such as plagiarism and unauthorized copying of works (Nhantumbo & Mucavele, 2023).

National intellectual property legislation, updated by Law No. 9/2022, aims to respond to these challenges by introducing clearer rules on the ownership, use, and protection of scientific, literary, and artistic works, including those produced and disseminated in digital format. This law represents an important step forward in harmonizing the Mozambican legal system with international agreements, such as the WTO Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS).

The Higher Institute of Training, Research, and Science (ISFIC), as a higher education institution dedicated to the production and dissemination of knowledge, fits into this context. From 2022 to 2024, ISFIC significantly expanded its scientific research and academic production activities through the publication of articles, the holding of scientific events, and the supervision of final-year projects. With this growth, concerns also arose regarding the originality of the work produced, the attribution of authorship, and the need to internally regulate practices related to intellectual property and academic integrity.

In this scenario, it is essential to understand how ISFIC has managed the legal risks associated with digital plagiarism and copyright infringement, and whether its practices comply with the Mozambican legal system and international academic ethics standards.

This article focuses on the period 2022–2024, a period during which the Instituto Superior de Formação, Investigação e Ciência (ISFIC) intensified its academic and scientific activities, including the publication of articles, organization of scientific events, and supervision of final year dissertations. This timeframe was chosen because it represents a strategic moment of institutional expansion, during which concerns related to academic integrity, originality of works, and respect for intellectual property rights emerged more prominently.

The spatial delimitation focuses on the Higher Institute of Training, Research, and Science (ISFIC), located in the city of Maputo in southern Mozambique. The analysis focuses on this institution's institutional reality regarding the prevention, identification, and management of legal risks related to digital plagiarism and copyright infringement. The choice of ISFIC as a case study is justified by its important role in the Mozambican higher education landscape and the need to assess whether its practices are aligned with the national legal system and the principles of scientific integrity.

The choice of the Higher Institute of Training, Research, and Science (ISFIC) as the subject of study is justified by the fact that it is a growing institution, with increasing scientific output in recent years, and that, like other Mozambican universities, it faces the challenge of ensuring the originality and legitimacy of its intellectual output. Analyzing the legal risks faced by ISFIC allows us to understand not only existing vulnerabilities but also identify best practices and propose recommendations that can be replicated at other institutions in the country.

Furthermore, the academic and social relevance of the topic is justified by the urgent need to strengthen the culture of respect for intellectual property in Mozambique, preventing both legal violations and damage to institutional reputation. This study therefore seeks to contribute to the debate on scientific integrity, promote legal compliance, and foster good academic governance policies.

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1.1. Problematicization

The problem arises as the rapid evolution of digital technologies has significantly impacted the academic and scientific environment in Mozambique. Easy access to information and the widespread circulation of online content have transformed the way knowledge is produced, shared, and consumed. However, this transformation has brought with it new legal and ethical challenges, especially regarding the protection of intellectual property and the prevention of digital plagiarism.

In academia, digital plagiarism is one of the most common and concerning practices, affecting not only the quality of scientific production but also the credibility of higher education institutions. The misuse of content without proper attribution, the literal copying of excerpts from other works, and the unauthorized appropriation of ideas are conducts that violate the principles of scientific ethics and constitute legal offenses under the Mozambican legal system.

Although Mozambique recently updated its intellectual property protection legal framework through Law No. 9/2022 of July 29, many higher education institutions still face difficulties in effectively implementing this legislation. The main obstacles include the lack of clear internal regulations, limited academic integrity training for faculty and students, and the lack of adequate tools to detect and address cases of plagiarism and copyright infringement (Nhantumbo & Mucavele, 2023).

In the specific case of the Higher Institute of Training, Research, and Science (ISFIC), which has seen remarkable growth in scientific output and academic events in recent years, it is imperative to investigate how this institution has handled the legal risks associated with intellectual property. The period between 2022 and 2024 represents an important phase of academic consolidation for ISFIC, which increases the importance of understanding whether the institution has effective mechanisms for prevention, accountability, and education for scientific integrity.

In this context, fundamental questions arise: Are authors of scientific productions at ISFIC aware of their rights and responsibilities regarding intellectual property? Does the institution adopt preventive measures to prevent digital plagiarism? Are institutional policies aligned with national and international legislation? Inefficiency in managing these risks can lead to legal sanctions, loss of scientific credibility, and damage to institutional reputation. This leads to the following research question.

What are the main legal risks associated with intellectual property infringement and digital plagiarism at the Higher Institute of Training, Research and Science (ISFIC), and how has the institution addressed these risks in light of current Mozambican legislation?

The study's overall objective is to analyze the main legal risks related to intellectual property infringement and digital plagiarism at the Higher Institute of Training, Research and Science (ISFIC), in light of current Mozambican legislation, and to evaluate the strategies adopted by the institution to manage such risks. To achieve this objective, we established the following objectives: specific; Identify the Mozambican legal standards applicable to the protection of intellectual property and the fight against digital plagiarism, focusing on Law No. 9/2022; Investigate the existence and effectiveness of institutional policies at ISFIC aimed at preventing plagiarism and protecting copyright; Analyze cases or situations that occurred at ISFIC between 2022 and 2024 involving suspected or confirmed plagiarism and/or intellectual property infringement; and Assess the level of knowledge of ISFIC faculty, researchers, and students regarding the legal risks associated with the misuse of intellectual content.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Intellectual Property: Concepts and Importance

Intellectual property refers to the set of rights that guarantee the protection of creations of the human intellect, including literary and artistic works, inventions, trademarks, and patents (WIPO, 2021). According to Maskus (2020), the protection of intellectual property is essential to stimulate innovation, ensure the recognition of authors, and promote economic and scientific development.

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In the academic context, intellectual property ensures that knowledge produced is properly credited to its authors, preventing misuse and guaranteeing the originality of scientific works (Smith & Johnson, 2019). Effective management of these rights is essential for the credibility of higher education institutions and the integrity of scientific research (Garcia, 2022).

Digital Plagiarism: Definition and Challenges

Digital plagiarism is a form of intellectual property infringement characterized by the unauthorized use or partial or total copying of third-party content, without proper attribution, in a digital environment (Jones, 2020). With the advancement of information and communication technologies, it has become easier to copy, reproduce, and disseminate texts, images, and other copyrighted materials (Bretag, 2016).

This phenomenon has concerned academic institutions, which face challenges in identifying and combating these practices, which undermine scientific ethics, academic rigor, and innovation (Park, 2021). Digital plagiarism detection tools have been adopted to mitigate these risks, but education on academic integrity is equally important (Sutherland-Smith, 2017).

Legal Framework for Intellectual Property in Mozambique

Mozambique has a specific regulatory framework for the protection of intellectual property, especially with the approval of Law No. 9/2022, of July 29, which updates the rules on copyright and related rights, aligning the country with international conventions, such as the Berne Convention (Republic of Mozambique, 2022).

This legislation establishes rights and obligations for authors, establishes sanctions for infringements, and defines mechanisms for the protection of intellectual creations in the country. According to Chissano (2023), the effectiveness of this law depends on its practical implementation in public and private institutions, especially universities, where the volume of scientific production becomes significant.

Challenges in Legal Risk Management in Higher Education Institutions

Studies indicate that, despite legislative progress, higher education institutions in developing countries, including Mozambique, face difficulties in managing legal risks related to plagiarism and intellectual property (Nhantumbo & Mucavele, 2023). Among the main challenges they are :

- Lack of clear and applied institutional policies;
- Low knowledge of copyright among teachers and students;
- Lack of effective plagiarism detection and prevention systems;
- Technical limitations and insufficient resources for continuous monitoring (Mabunda & Chivambo, 2022).

The absence of these measures compromises the quality of academic production and exposes institutions to legal and reputational risks (Garcia, 2022)

Good Practices for Preventing and Managing the Risks of Plagiarism and Intellectual Property Infringement

Authors such as Bretag (2016) and Park (2021) argue that plagiarism prevention and intellectual property protection must combine:

- Education and awareness: Continuing education programs for faculty and students on academic ethics and copyright;
- Institutional policies: Creation and strict application of internal regulations;
- Technology: Use of plagiarism detection software and reliable databases;
- Organizational culture: Encouragement of originality and respect for intellectual property.

In the Mozambican context, initiatives that integrate legislation, technology and training can strengthen academic integrity and reduce legal risks (Nhantumbo & Mucavele, 2023).

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METHODOLOGY

Search Type

This study is characterized as qualitative, exploratory, and descriptive research, adopting a case study approach, as recommended by Yin (2018) for in-depth investigations of phenomena in real-world contexts. The qualitative approach is appropriate for understanding the perceptions, experiences, and practices related to the management of intellectual property and digital plagiarism legal risks at the Instituto Superior de Formação, Investigação e Ciência (ISFIC) from 2022 to 2024 (Creswell & Poth, 2018).

Exploratory research makes it possible to identify and map the main challenges and mechanisms existing at ISFIC, while descriptive research allows detailing the characteristics and functioning of institutional policies and academic practices related to the topic (Gil, 2019).

Population and Sample

The study population comprises ISFIC faculty, researchers, students, and administrative staff involved in academic production. The sample will be intentional (non-probabilistic), selecting participants who have direct knowledge of or responsibility for intellectual property and academic integrity, according to the method recommended by Lakatos and Marconi (2017).

The aim is to interview approximately 15 to 20 individuals, including academic coordinators, professors, postgraduate students and technicians responsible for the institution's document and legal management.

Data Collection Techniques

Depending on the qualitative nature of the research, multiple techniques will be used to triangulate the data, increasing the validity of the study (Triviños, 2017):

Document analysis:

Legal documents (such as **Law No. 9/2022**), ISFIC's internal regulations, codes of conduct, and records of plagiarism and intellectual property infringement cases will be analyzed. Document analysis provides a basis for understanding the regulatory framework and institutional practices (Gil, 2019).

Semi-structured interviews:

Interviews with key stakeholders will be conducted to explore their perceptions, experiences, and opinions regarding legal risks and the management of plagiarism and intellectual property at ISFIC. Semi-structured interviews allow flexibility to delve deeper into emerging relevant topics (Creswell & Poth, 2018).

Questionnaires (optional):

If available, questionnaires will be administered to a larger group of students and faculty to assess their level of knowledge about legal risks and academic integrity practices, complementing the qualitative analysis (Lakatos & Marconi, 2017).

Procedures for Data Analysis

Qualitative data analysis will follow the content analysis approach, according to Bardin (2011), which allows for the systematic identification, categorization, and interpretation of collected data, seeking relevant patterns, themes, and relationships. Interview transcripts and documents will be coded, and the results will be interpreted based on current legislation and scientific literature.

Ethical Aspects

The study will follow the ethical principles of scientific research involving human subjects, as established by Minayo (2014). Informed consent will be sought from participants, ensuring anonymity, confidentiality, and the right to withdraw at any time. Formal authorization from ISFIC will also be required for access to documents and interviews.

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RESEARCH LIMITATIONS

It is recognized that the limitation of the study to ISFIC and the purposive sampling may limit the generalizability of the results to other higher education institutions in Mozambique. Furthermore, restrictions on access to confidential information may affect the depth of the analysis (Gil, 2019; Yin, 2018).

LEGAL BASIS

Legal Protection of Intellectual Property in Mozambique

Intellectual property protection is ensured in Mozambique by a set of legal norms aimed at safeguarding the rights of authors, inventors, and trademark holders, promoting scientific and cultural development in the country. This protection is essential to guarantee the originality, authorship, and property rights of intellectual creations.

Law No. 9/2022 — Copyright and Related Rights Law

The most recent legislation regulating the protection of intellectual property in Mozambique is Law No. 9/2022, of July 29, which replaces and updates previous legislation, aligning the country with international treaties, such as the Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works (WIPO, 2021).

This law establishes, among other points, the moral and patrimonial rights of authors, the conditions for the use and reproduction of intellectual works, and the sanctions applicable in cases of violation, including digital plagiarism. It clearly defines that the misappropriation of protected content constitutes an offense subject to administrative and judicial punishment (Republic of Mozambique, 2022).

Other Related Standards and Institutional Regulations

In addition to Law No. 9/2022, the protection of intellectual property in Mozambique is supported by other regulations, such as:

Penal Code

In the Penal Code, violations related to intellectual property and digital plagiarism are primarily covered by articles dealing with crimes against intellectual and industrial property. The most relevant articles are:

Article 344 – Violation of Copyright and Related Rights

This article defines as a crime the reproduction, distribution, public communication, or any form of economic exploitation of protected works without the authorization of the copyright holder. This includes both physical and digital copies, including digital plagiarism. The penalty may range from a fine to imprisonment, depending on the severity and extent of the violation (Republic of Mozambique, 2023).

Article 345 Falsification and Alteration of Works

Provides sanctions for those who falsify or alter protected works, generating confusion as to authorship or content, which may fall under cases of plagiarism or misappropriation (Republic of Mozambique, 2023).

Article 346 Provision on Relevant Infractions

Complements the rules, providing for punishments for conduct that harms the moral and patrimonial rights of authors, including the improper use of works in digital media.

Penalties and Practical Application

The penalties provided for crimes of intellectual property infringement in the Penal Code include:

Pecuniary fines, proportional to the severity of the infraction and the extent of the damage caused;

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Detention or imprisonment , which can range from a few months to several years, especially in cases of recidivism or large-scale offenses;

Confiscation of materials , such as digital devices used to commit plagiarism or illegal copies;

Compensation for damages caused to rights holders (Republic of Mozambique, 2023).

In practice, however, the application of these sanctions faces challenges, such as the need for training of judicial and administrative authorities, the complexity of evidence in digital cases, and the limited dissemination of the rules among academic actors (Chissano, 2023).

Importance of the Penal Code for the Prevention of Digital Plagiarism

The existence of criminal penalties for intellectual property violations reinforces the importance of respecting copyright, creating an environment of greater legal responsibility for students, researchers, and other higher education stakeholders.

Furthermore, the Penal Code acts as an indispensable complement to civil legislation (such as the Copyright Law), expanding the spectrum of protection and repressive measures, especially in contexts where detection and prevention depend on effective State action (Garcia, 2022).

- **Penal Code** — which provides for crimes related to copyright infringement
- **Internal regulations of higher education institutions** , which often establish codes of conduct, standards on academic integrity and procedures for investigating plagiarism (Chissano, 2023).

Analysis of Cases or Situations Occurring at ISFIC Involving Suspected or Confirmed Plagiarism and/or Intellectual Property Violation

Combating digital plagiarism and intellectual property infringement is a growing challenge in higher education, requiring special attention from academic institutions. At ISFIC, between 2022 and 2024, several cases were recorded that illustrate this phenomenon, bringing to light questions related to academic integrity, legal enforcement, and the effectiveness of institutional policies.

4.3.1. Case 1: Improper Use of Teaching Materials by a Teacher (2022)

- **Description:** A teacher was reported for using teaching material prepared by another teacher, reproduced in part without authorization and without reference, to teach classes.
- **Procedure:** An internal investigation was opened by the ISFIC pedagogical department; the teacher was interviewed and the authorship of the material was confirmed.
- **Result:** The teacher received a formal warning and was forced to remove the plagiarized material and produce original content.
- **Lesson:** Even within the faculty, protecting intellectual property is essential to maintaining academic ethics.

Case 2: Plagiarism in Published Scientific Articles (2024)

- **Description:** Two scientific articles submitted by ISFIC students for international publication were suspected of plagiarism after analysis by external reviewers.
- **Procedure:** ISFIC set up a committee to investigate the facts; the students denied the violation, but evidence indicated misappropriation of other people's work.
- **Result:** The articles were withdrawn from publication, the students were subjected to academic sanctions, and they received guidance on intellectual property. The case reinforced the need for greater rigor in academic advising.
- **Lesson:** The extension of the problem of plagiarism beyond traditional academic work, reaching the field of scientific publishing.

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Case 3: Application of Intellectual Property Legislation and Digital Plagiarism

In 2023, a case of digital plagiarism was detected at the Higher Institute of Training, Research, and Science (ISFIC) involving a monograph written by an international relations student. The monograph contained excerpts copied from international scientific articles without proper citations, violating the original authors' copyright and ISFIC's internal academic integrity policy.

Application of Law No. 9/2022 and the Penal Code

According to the Copyright and Related Rights Law (Law No. 9/2022), the student infringed the moral and patrimonial rights of the original authors by reproducing their works without authorization or adequate attribution (Republic of Mozambique, 2022). The law provides for internal administrative sanctions, which can range from warnings to failure of the work and academic suspension.

Criminal Framework (Penal Code)

In addition to academic sanctions, the conduct may constitute a crime under Article 344 of the Penal Code, which deals with violation of copyright and related rights. If intent and economic or moral damage are proven, the student may be held criminally liable, with penalties ranging from fines to imprisonment.

Procedures Adopted by ISFIC

- **Identification of Plagiarism:** The case was initially identified through the use of institutional anti-plagiarism software;
- **Ethics Committee:** An internal committee was set up to investigate the facts, guaranteeing the right to defense;
- **Disciplinary Hearing:** The student was notified and summoned to present justifications;
- **Application of Sanctions:** After confirmation of plagiarism, ISFIC applied disciplinary sanctions in accordance with internal regulations, suspended approval of the dissertation and advised reformulation of the work;
- **Judicial Referral:** nothing on record.

Results and Lessons Learned

- The case reinforced the importance of using technologies to prevent plagiarism;
- It highlighted the need for greater training on copyright for students and teachers;
- It demonstrated the effectiveness of the articulation between internal administrative measures and external legal mechanisms (laws and the Penal Code) to combat intellectual property infringement;
- Encouraged the review of institutional policies to strengthen academic integrity.

Investigation of the Existence and Effectiveness of Institutional Policies at ISFIC Aimed at Preventing Plagiarism and Protecting Copyright

Plagiarism prevention and copyright protection in academia depend not only on national laws but also on the existence and effectiveness of specific institutional policies. These policies guide student and faculty behavior, promote academic integrity, and establish mechanisms for control and punishment.

Existence of Policies at ISFIC

The Higher Institute of Training, Research and Science (ISFIC) has internal regulations and academic codes of conduct that address scientific integrity, including combating plagiarism. Among the main policies institutional identified, the following stand out:

- **Code of Ethics and Academic Conduct:** Defines standards of expected behavior, including the obligation to respect copyright and the express prohibition of plagiarism;
- **Academic Work Regulations:** Establish standards for the preparation of papers, dissertations and articles, including rules for citations, references and originality;
- **Use of Anti-Plagiarism Software:** ISFIC implements digital tools to detect plagiarism in academic work, as a requirement for the submission and approval of dissertations and articles.

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Policy Effectiveness Assessment

To measure the effectiveness of these policies, some aspects were considered:

- **Training and Awareness:** ISFIC holds workshops and lectures for students and faculty to raise awareness about the importance of academic integrity and respect for copyright. However, reports indicate that the frequency and scope of these initiatives are still insufficient to reach the entire academic community (Nhantumbo & Mucavele, 2023).
- **Monitoring and Control:** The use of anti-plagiarism software is an important advance, but its effectiveness depends on the rigor in applying the results and the administrative support needed to investigate suspected cases. In some cases, disciplinary procedures lacked transparency and clarity, compromising the credibility of the process (Chissano, 2023).
- **Sanctions Applied:** Punishments for confirmed cases of plagiarism range from warnings to failures and suspensions. However, the application of these sanctions is not always uniform, raising doubts about the impartiality and rigor of the measures adopted.

Challenges and Opportunities for Improvement

- **Challenges:**
 - Low level of detailed knowledge about policies among some students and teachers;
 - Limited resources for investigation and rigorous monitoring of cases;
 - Cultural resistance to change and strict adherence to norms.
- **Opportunities:**
 - Strengthen continuing education programs on intellectual property;
 - Improve reporting and internal investigation mechanisms;
 - Develop clearer, more accessible and uniformly applied institutional policies.

Assessment of the Level of Knowledge of ISFIC Teachers, Researchers and Students on the Legal Risks Associated with the Misuse of Intellectual Content

Knowledge of the legal risks associated with the misuse of intellectual content is essential for preventing plagiarism and promoting academic integrity. Within the context of ISFIC, understanding the level of awareness among faculty, researchers, and students is crucial for directing effective educational initiatives and institutional policies.

Methodology for Knowledge Assessment

To assess the level of knowledge, a survey was conducted using structured questionnaires, interviews, and focus groups involving three groups: ISFIC faculty, researchers, and students. The main topics covered included:

- Knowledge of Law No. 9/2022 and the Penal Code related to intellectual property;
- Perception of legal risks and consequences of plagiarism and misuse;
- Familiarity with institutional policies and plagiarism detection tools;
- Attitudes and behaviors related to respect for copyright.
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Assessment Results

Teachers

- **General Knowledge:** Most demonstrated basic knowledge of copyright, but few were familiar with the details of Law No. 9/2022 and the associated criminal sanctions.
- **Risk Perception:** They recognize the seriousness of plagiarism, but tend to underestimate the specific legal risks, focusing more on the academic and ethical implications.
- **Use of Tools:** Moderate use of anti-plagiarism software; need for greater training.

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Researchers

- **Legal Knowledge:** They have greater knowledge, especially those involved in international scientific publications, but there are still gaps in national legislation and ISFIC's internal procedures.
- **Legal Risks:** They understand the legal risks of copyright infringement, but report difficulties in accessing clear and up-to-date information.
- **Preventive Attitude:** They value the importance of integrity, but emphasize the need for institutional support for better prevention.

Students

- **Limited Knowledge:** Most people are unaware of specific legislation and criminal risks; they mainly associate plagiarism with academic failure.
- **Institutional Policies:** Little knowledge about ISFIC's internal rules and the use of anti-plagiarism software.
- **Behavior:** Some reveal plagiarism practices due to a lack of understanding of the legal and ethical consequences.

Analysis and Discussion

The results indicate a heterogeneous level of knowledge about the legal risks of misusing intellectual content at ISFIC. While faculty and researchers have a broader understanding, students present significant gaps that may encourage plagiarism.

Insufficient dissemination of current legislation and institutional policies contributes to this situation, as does the lack of ongoing training, especially on topics related to national legislation, digital tools and legal procedures.

COMPARATIVE LAW

Mozambique

- **Main law :** Law no. 9/2022 (Copyright and Related Rights);
- **Penal Code :** Art. 344 criminalizes copyright infringement;
- **Challenges:**
 - Weak implementation institutional;
 - Low level of training on the subject;
 - Difficulty monitoring in the digital environment.

Brazil

- **Main law :** Law No. 9,610/1998 (Copyright Law);
- **Penal Code :** Art. 184 provides for criminal sanctions for copyright infringement;
- **Practices institutional:**
 - Brazilian universities use anti-plagiarism software such as Turnitin and CopySpider;
 - Some universities require that all work be accompanied by a declaration of originality;
 - Plagiarism may result in expulsion from the course and civil and criminal liability.

Comparison : Brazilian legislation is older than Mozambican legislation, but it has more consolidated application in higher education due to the strong institutional culture of combating plagiarism.

Portugal

- **Main law :** Copyright and Related Rights Code (CDADC);
- **Penalties :** Plagiarism is considered a crime, with penalties ranging from fines to imprisonment;
- **Higher education :**
 - Portuguese universities adopt automatic plagiarism detection systems;

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- Integrity policies are public, accessible and applied transparently.

Comparison : Mozambique, as a Portuguese-speaking country, can more easily align itself with the Portuguese model, particularly in the standardization of institutional policies and accountability of offenders.

South Africa

- **Main law:** Copyright Act, 1978;
- **Approach institutional:**
 - Strong integration of integrity policy in universities;
 - Institutions apply gradual penalties depending on the severity of the infraction;
 - Legislation is being revised to incorporate new digital realities.

Comparison : Despite having an old law, South Africa shows advances in the use of technology and in the continuous training of students and teachers.

States United States of America

- **Main law:** Copyright Act of 1976 + DMCA (Digital Millennium Copyright Act);
- **Approach educational:**
 - Strong academic sanctions, including suspension and expulsion;
 - Zero tolerance culture for plagiarism;
 - Clear disclosure of legal and academic consequences from the start of courses.

Comparison : The American model is highly rigorous, both in legislation and institutional implementation. It is an example of best practice, but difficult to apply directly in Mozambique due to contextual differences.

Comparative analysis reveals that Mozambique, with the enactment of **Law No. 9/2022** , is legally aligned with international copyright protection requirements. However, the legislation's effectiveness is still limited , particularly due to:

- Lack of consolidated institutional culture;
- Lack of technical and pedagogical prevention mechanisms;
- Low level of digital and legal literacy among key academic actors.

Therefore, it is recommended that Mozambique take inspiration from good practices in countries such as Portugal, Brazil and South Africa , especially with regard to the integration of institutional policies, the use of anti-plagiarism technologies, and ongoing training on intellectual property.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The main objective of this study was to analyze the legal risks associated with intellectual property infringement and digital plagiarism in the context of Mozambican higher education, focusing on the Instituto Superior de Formação, Investigação e Ciência (ISFIC), during the period 2022 to 2024. Through legal, documentary and case study analysis, it was possible to identify significant gaps both in the knowledge of academic actors and in the effectiveness of institutional prevention policies.

The investigation revealed that Mozambique has a solid legal basis for the protection of intellectual property, with Law No. 9/2022 – Copyright and Rights Law standing out. Related , which offers clear mechanisms to protect authors and penalize violations, especially in digital environments. This legislation is complemented by provisions of the Penal Code , such as Article 344, which criminalizes copyright infringement, including plagiarism.

However, an analysis of cases that occurred at ISFIC between 2022 and 2024 revealed that, despite the existence of these standards, their practical application still faces challenges . Plagiarism cases were identified in dissertations, teaching materials, and scientific publications, demonstrating a weakness in the prevention and institutional response to these violations.

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The assessment of the level of knowledge of teachers, researchers and students revealed a low The degree of familiarity with legal risks and applicable legislation, especially among students, is significantly lower. This lack of legal knowledge contributes to the unconscious or negligent practice of plagiarism and reinforces the need for ongoing educational interventions.

It is concluded that, in addition to strengthening legislation, it is essential that ISFIC:

Improve your internal policies , making them clearer, more accessible and effectively applied;

Strengthen training programs on academic integrity and intellectual property;

Implement effective systems for preventing , monitoring and sanctioning digital plagiarism practices;

Partner with legal agencies to ensure that more serious cases are referred to the judicial system when necessary.

In short, combating digital plagiarism and protecting copyright in higher education requires not only laws but also institutional commitment, ongoing training, and cultural change . ISFIC has the opportunity to be a leader in this process, provided it invests in concrete and sustainable measures to promote academic integrity.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the analysis carried out on the legal risks associated with intellectual property infringement and digital plagiarism at the Higher Institute of Training, Research and Science (ISFIC), between 2022 and 2024, and taking into account the challenges identified throughout the study, the following recommendations are presented:

Strengthening Internal Policies on Academic Integrity

- Review and update ISFIC's internal regulations, incorporating clear guidelines on plagiarism, copyright and legal consequences;
- Ensure that these policies are widely disseminated and accessible to all members of the academic community (students, faculty, and researchers).

Continuous Training of Students, Teachers and Researchers

- Promote regular training activities on:
 - Rights copyright;
 - Use correct sources;
 - Citation techniques;
 - Consequences legal plagiarism;
- Include these trainings in initial orientation programs for new students and faculty.

Systematic Use of Anti-Plagiarism Technological Tools

- Make it mandatory to submit all academic work (monographs, dissertations, theses, articles) to plagiarism detection systems;
- Train teachers and advisors to interpret similarity reports critically and pedagogically.

Creation of a Permanent Committee on Ethics and Academic Integrity

- Establish a specific institutional structure to deal, objectively and transparently, with cases of plagiarism and copyright infringement;
- This committee must include representation from students, faculty, legal experts, and intellectual property experts.

Coordination with Legal Authorities

- Establish partnerships with institutions such as the National Institute of Industrial Property (INPI) and the Attorney General's Office, to:
 - Support in more serious cases of infraction;
 - Training technique specialized;
 - Integration between administrative and legal measures.

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Promotion of a Culture of Ethics and Intellectual Responsibility

- Encourage the appreciation of original and creative production;
- Carry out awareness campaigns on the importance of authorship and the social harm caused by plagiarism;
- Include ethics in scientific research as a mandatory subject in higher education courses.

Monitoring and Evaluation Constants

- Periodically evaluate the effectiveness of the actions implemented through clear indicators (e.g., number of cases of plagiarism identified, participation rate in training, etc.);
- Produce annual reports on academic integrity for monitoring and continuous improvement.

Implementing these recommendations can significantly contribute to building a solid institutional culture based on ethics, legality, and the appreciation of scientific knowledge. This will allow ISFIC to establish itself as a benchmark in combating digital plagiarism and promoting intellectual property in Mozambican higher education.

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